

Poster Abstract: Data Leakage Detection Algorithm Based on Sequences of Activities

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Abstract. In this paper we propose an algorithm for data leakage detection. This algorithm works with historical data of the activities of authorized users in a computer system. This information gathers data of the hour of the accesses, duration, day of the week, operation, table that has been accessed, etc. They have been provided by a governmental institution at Ecuador. The procedure has two phases. The first one is based on the calculation of the probability of each activity that is carried out by each user. These activities are for instance to modify a file, delete, copy, etc. The different activities at different times are codified by an integer or character. The Page Rank algorithm is used to calculate the probability of every activity. But the activities form sequences, that is, during a session (time between the user logs in and logs out), the user carries out different activities, one after another. These sequences of activities may have different length. The probability of each sequence of activities is then calculated by applying the Bayes' theorem. The minimum of these conditional probabilities is obtained and set as a threshold, r_{min} . If a new chain of activities, s_i , is introduced in the detection leakage system, first of all the page rank is applied and then the Bayes' law, so a probability of that particular sequence of activities for that user is obtained, let's say p_i . This probability, p_i , is compared to the threshold, r_{min} . If it does not surpass it, a leakage warning message is generated. Otherwise, the sequence of activities goes to the second phase of the procedure. The sequence of activities that is being tested is then compared to all the sequences of activities of that particular user that are stored in the historical database. Applying the Smith and Waterman algorithm, a similarity score is obtained for this sentence regarding the rest of the sequences previously carried out by the user. This algorithm determines similar regions between two strings comparing segments of all possible lengths and optimizes the similarity measure. If the score is higher than a second threshold, let's say that there are more than n characters (codified activities) that are the same than another sequence of the same user, the activity can be considered right; otherwise it may be a leakage. Although this algorithm is still being developing, its main contribution is the way it handles different lengths of the sequences and how it works with a behavioral pattern of each user.

Keywords: Data Leakage Detection, Page Rank algorithm, Bayes' Theorem, Smith and Waterman algorithm, behavioral pattern.

Poster Abstract: Data Leakage Detection Algorithm including Sequences of Activities

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ABSTRACT

Information leakage is a current problem that worries most public and private institutions around the world. Data is one of the most important assets for an institution. Therefore it is important to design and implement computational tools in order to avoid leakage, loss or modification of crucial information. This problem is especially critical when data leakage is caused by authorized people.

In this paper we propose an algorithm for data leakage detection. The algorithm is based on the one hand on the probability of certain activities that authorized users usually do (such as modify a file, delete, copy, etc.). On the other hand, it also provides a ranking of similarity between the sequence of activities of particular users, that is, the frequency and order of these activities.

CURRENT SCENARIO (MATERIALS)

The public sector of the Republic of Ecuador, as any other government, has information systems of utmost importance. It is necessary to have an adequate control even of the authorized users' activities who have access to such information.

The information used in this study is the sequences of activities carried out by public servants who have authorized access to the governmental databases (modify a file, copy, insert, etc). This information gathers data of the hour of the accesses, duration, day of the week, operation, table that has been accessed, etc. It has been codified as a string of characters.

METHODS

- **Page Rank algorithm** allows us to obtain the probabilities of each of the activities undertaken by the users.
- **Bayes' Theorem** gives the conditional probability of a sequence of activities of a particular user.
- **Smith and Waterman algorithm** determines similar regions between two codified sequences of activities comparing segments of all possible lengths and giving a score.

USER BEHAVIOUR

The user behavior is dynamic and the number of activities during a session is variable

Activities within a user session in a computer system has the following structure

ALGORITHM

- Phase 1:**
- 1) Page Rank: activity's probability $P_i(a_i)$
 - 2) Bayes' Law: conditional probability of a sequence of activities of an user $P_i(s_i)$
 - 3) Evaluation of a new sequence of activities s_i
 - Set a threshold as a minimum (r_{min})
 - If $P_i(s_i) < r_{min}$ warning leakage otherwise go to Phase 2
- Phase 2:**
- 1) Smith & Waterman algorithm: score of similarity of that sequence $S_i(s_i)$
 - If $S_i(s_i) < n$ warning leakage otherwise O.K.

RESULTS

CONCLUSIONS

- The proposed algorithm handles different lengths of the sequences
- It works with a behavioral pattern of each user
- Preliminary results are encouraging